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POSSIBILITIES OF THE “QUEST” TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article gives information about the possibility of using the "Quest" pedagogical technology in secondary education, gives its detailed characteristics and provides a description of the quest conducted in the 9th grade of secondary school in English classes and after school hours. It is noted that this technology is quite applicable in teaching foreign languages at school, since it is aimed at solving a set of tasks that local education is facing currently.

Keywords: *secondary education, teaching foreign languages, pedagogical technologies, project activity, educational quest.*

INTRODUCTION:

The processes of globalization and the active development of technology are affecting almost all spheres of life, including school education. In response to these challenges of the time, the education system around the world is undergoing significant transformations so that it fully meets the requirements of modern society. In secondary education, there are changes in learning objectives, new methods and technologies are being applied, online technologies have a great influence on the essence of the educational process, the design and content of the educational environment are going through the transformation.

These processes are not least due to the fact that at the moment a new generation of young people, who are called "centenials", is studying at school. That is why, according to the researchers, changes in the education system should now take into account the social and psychological characteristics of the new generation, and the methodological search should be directed to the field of those learning technologies that would correspond to changing students.

In this regard, technologies that, on the one hand, meet the needs of students, and on the other, which can provide training for workers who are capable of designing new types of activities in the modern world, create successful businesses, to solve urgent problems in conditions characterized by a high level of competition. Today, the school can no longer simply serve as a transmitter of knowledge: the teacher now becomes an assistant to the student in the independent production of knowledge. Today, direct memorization of previously known material is giving way to critical and creative thinking, group work, and communication for obtaining the information. In the educational process, the most important skills are the ability to independently acquire knowledge based on search and analysis, that is, research activities.

It seems that these tasks can be solved using the educational technology "Quest". Working with the quest, various disciplines and knowledge are integrated, and the main focus falls on solving a specific task. Such technology is necessary for the adequate formation of the key competencies of a modern young person.

Ideologically, the "Quest" technology correlates with the design technology, which dates back to the 1920s in the USA, when it was proposed to build training not on the principle of "from theory to practice", but on the need to solve a certain task. The essence of the method lies in the fact that in order to achieve a given final result, the student is required to apply a number of interdisciplinary competencies, independent work, reflection, planning possible results and much more.

Among one of the forms of implementation of project activities is the technology "Quest"(quest – search). The quest gained special popularity at the end of the twentieth century, with the advent of the eponymous genre of computer games, which, as a rule, were based on the story of a character who needed to achieve a certain ultimate goal by overcoming a number of obstacles and solving riddles and puzzles.

The essence of the quest remained unchanged when Bernie Dodge first mentioned it as a learning technology in 1995. At that time, he created a unique educational project where students had to solve the problem by using all kinds of resources, including the Internet, and going from stage to stage, to achieve the final goal.

Today, the quest used in education is characterized by the presence of a story, elements of a role-playing game, as well as various tasks, the solution of which is necessary to advance along a given plot.

Subsequently, Professor Tom March proposed a more detailed description of this technology, highlighting a special type of quest, namely, a web-quest. The fundamental difference of the web-quest is that all tasks in it are completely based on the selected online platform or website on the Internet, and students can be involved in solving the problem remotely. The presence of the teacher is minimized and limited only by the provision of resources, usually in the form of hyperlinks needed during work. Receiving feedback can also be done outside the audience.

T. March claims that the web-quest's salient characteristics are as follows:

1. The web-quest is built around an engaging and unique job that is closely related to reality – the things that people see and do on a daily basis.

2. The web quest involves intensive intellectual activity (its analysis, synthesis, critical evaluation, etc.), and not just generalization of information.

3. An online quest cannot be finished without actively using the Internet. Numerous interpretations of these notions can be found because research in the field of quest and web-quest technology has only lately been performed in Russia. Ya.S. Bykhovsky defines a web-quest simply as "a website on the Internet that students work with, performing one or the another educational task". More precisely, M.V. Andreeva formulates this concept, considering that the web-quest represents a stage for organizing students' project activities on any topic using Internet resources.

It is known that in their educational activities, students today deal with a large number of research papers, the purpose of which is to search for and systematize information. The quest, in addition, allows students to use their imagination and skills to solve the issues.

Because the answers aren't known ahead of time, the students completing the quest can come up with something original and fresh. Only by applying creative thinking, students can achieve the final solution to their task. At the same time, while investigating a problem, students not only assimilate information: when they face conflicting opinions, they determine their position on a specific problem, formulate their point of view, enter into a discussion, defending their opinion.

An analysis of the literature shows that, according to various characteristics, scientists distinguish the following types of quests:

- by the form of the event – a computer game, a web-quest (when students search and analyze web resources and create a web product - a blog, a note, a website, etc.), a media quest (for example, photo and video quests), outdoor quests (in a park, in the yard, etc.) and combined quests;
- according to the mode of conducting – in real mode, in virtual mode and combined;
- by the time of implementation – short-term and long-term quests;
- according to the form of work – individual and group;

– by dominant activity – quest-research, information quest, creative quest, quest game, role

-playing quest – the structure of the plot is linear and nonlinear.

When describing the "quest" technology, it should be mentioned that it is carried out in multiple stages, which are executed as solo work at home and classroom work in the classroom, just like any other project activity.

As part of group work, students distribute roles and tasks among themselves, build execution tactics, and share results at all stages of work on the project.

The whole group is involved in the final stage: when discussing the results and evaluation. Independent work is those tasks that each student performs in their own team. The front of work between the students is clearly distributed and everyone is responsible for the result provided to them. The final result of the whole group depends on the work of each individual student.

The study of theoretical literature on the problem of using quest technology in the educational process made it possible to develop a quest called "OscarRace" in the course of the research. Based on the presented classifications, this quest can be characterized as a combined one, conducted in real time (within the framework of English language lessons and after school hours), short-term, group (in groups of 4-5 people) the project. According to the dominant type of activity, it can be attributed to the creative type of quests, since the result of the work is a project of a special format – a mini-film that students should shoot.

This quest is designed for students of the 9th grade of a secondary school, but it is possible to implement it in other classes, since the complexity of tasks can vary depending on the actual level of foreign language training of students.

The development of the quest pursued the achievement of the entire set of goals (personality-forming and practical subject). The objective is the development of foreign language communicative competence of students at the graduate level of primary school (integrative communication skills at the A2 level). Educational goals involve expanding the general ideas of schoolchildren about cinema and

cinematography, mastering the skills of searching and selecting relevant information and systematizing it.

Educational goals orient students to master the ability to define goals and the tasks of their own educational activities and choose the means to achieve them; to form the skills to plan and evaluate educational activities in accordance with the task and the theme of the conditions in which it is implemented; to develop skills to work in a team; as well as to foster a tolerant attitude to the traditions and culture of the countries of the foreign language being studied, to maintain interest in learning English. Developing goals make it possible to realize a sense of belonging to the fulfillment of a common cause; the importance of helping to master new useful and interesting information; provide conditions for realizing the creative potential of students, for their self-realization, in general.

The plot of the "OscarRace" quest is dedicated to the famous film company and the Oscar Film Award, which students can receive for creating their own film. The class is divided into mini-groups consisting of 4-5 people.

Each group is a film company that prepares its own film in order to subsequently present it as part of the competition program and compete for the Oscar statuette in the nomination "Best Film".

The quest is divided into three stages.

At the first stage, students form teams, determine the name and logo of their company, develop the plot and poster of the future film. At this stage, classroom work takes place, during which groups, moving from station to station, perform various tasks. For example, in task 1, students are invited to discuss various options for the name of their own film company.

Task 2

"Myfavouritemoviegenre" includes three audio excerpts, where the author briefly gives a description of one of the genres of cinema, without naming it. The task of the students becomes to give the name of the given genre and to argue their answer using keywords from the text. In task 3 "Movieposter", students are asked to choose a

representative from the team who can or just wants to try their drawing skills. He goes to the blackboard, where he is offered a piece of paper and a marker. At this time, the group is discussing the type of poster for their upcoming film (who is depicted, where, how it looks, what it does). Next, the group needs to describe their idea to the "artist" so that they get a ready-made poster. Task 4 "Howisthemoviemade?" assumes that students, using a number of links provided by the teacher, fill out a table that reflects the main stages of film creation and summarizes the key types of work related to filmmaking. In task 5 "Movieplot", each group is asked to come up with a plot for a future film and present it as a short story.

The second stage is extracurricular. Students have from one to two weeks for it. During this period of time, using their achievements made at the first stage, the group is working on its own mini-film. They are given full creative freedom, the only condition is that the duration of the video should not exceed 5 minutes.

The final, third stage, is devoted to watching, discussing and jointly evaluating the film presented by each group. This activity takes place in the classroom, when each student (according to pre-determined criteria) gets the opportunity to evaluate the work of his comrades. Based on the results achieved during the performance of the tasks of the first stage, and taking into account the collective assessment given for the film, the winning group is identified, which receives an Oscar statuette as a reward.

CONCLUSION:

The analysis of the quest shows that the goals and objectives set by us have been achieved. This is confirmed by the desire of schoolchildren to participate in a common cause, using their foreign language communication skills, the ability to work in a team (and some also have leadership qualities), a sense of responsibility for the final result, which were fully manifested in the process of completing tasks. The difficulties that were noted during the testing of the quest technology were mainly related to the novelty of this type of activity for students. Group work, although familiar to students, turned out to be an unusual format.

The development and testing of the quest has shown that this technology can be used at school. It meets the needs of modern schoolchildren in online technologies as a means of learning and can provide training for workers who are able to cope with the problems that people face in modern conditions.

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